

Views of Teachers of Students With Learning Disabilities Regarding Distance Education During COVID-19: A Case From Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

The outbreak of COVID-19 led to the closure all schools in Saudi Arabia, leaving them to rely mainly on distance education. The shift toward distance education is an unexpected experience for most teachers and students in Saudi schools. This experience is even more unique for teachers of students with learning disabilities (SLDs) because they represent the largest group with disabilities, spending at least 80% of their school day in general classrooms and 20% in the special education classrooms to receive face-to-face education. The goal in this research was to explore the opinions of teachers of SLDs working in public schools and using distance education with their SLDs during COVID-19. SWOT model for analysis and relevant literature were used to design a survey with a 5-point Likert scale to know teachers' opinions regarding: (a) strengths (S), (b) weaknesses (W), (c) threats (T), and (d) opportunities (O) of distance education. The relationship between the teachers' opinions regarding these dimensions and the type of distance education used before and during COVID-19 was also examined. The survey was distributed electronically to SLD teachers working in public schools located in Al-Ahsa Governorate. 42 teachers agreed to participate in the survey. Descriptive statistics and t-test were used to analyze the data. The results revealed that SLD teachers believe that distance education has advantages, disadvantages, promising trends, and challenges. Furthermore, there is a statistically significant relationship between the threats of using distance education with SLDs and the type of distance education that teachers used before COVID-19, and between the opportunities of distance education and the type of distance education used during COVID-19 at a level of $\alpha = 0.05$. Recommendations for future research and practices were highlighted to make informed decisions to maximize the opportunities of using distance education after COVID-19 by considering the voices of SLD teachers.

Introduction

The COVID-19 crisis could change the how teachers perceive traditional face-to-face and distance education for all students, especially for those with learning disabilities, and especially if their disabilities represent the highest incidences of disabilities in Saudi public schools (Abunyan, 2019). Distance education during COVID-19 can be described as an unexpected and unique experience for students with learning disabilities (SLDs) as well as for their teachers because of the full reliance on in-person education before COVID-19. The process of transformation began when the World Health Organization (WHO) declared a global emergency regarding the COVID-19 outbreak after it emerged on January 30, 2020 and classified it as a global pandemic on March 11, 2020. According to a report issued by United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2020) entitled "Education Disorder Due to the New Coronavirus and Overcoming It," the virus has caused a considerable number of students to drop out of school around the world. The report indicated that more than 100 countries had closed their educational institutions, affecting more than half of the world's students. The WHO also showed that more than 213 countries around the world, including Saudi Arabia, had been affected by the virus.

Because COVID-19 does not recognize the barriers of time and space, educational decisions in Saudi Arabia must overcome these barriers to continue the educational process, taking into account the health and safety of students as a priority. Based on the precautionary measures recommended by government authorities, and as part of its determined efforts to control the virus and prevent its spread, face-to-face education was suspended until further notice in all regions and governorates on March 14, 2020. Accordingly, the Ministry of Education (MOE) instructed schools to activate distance education during the suspension period. The Saudi MOE (2020a, 2020f) appointed a committee to provide classes for all students, including SLDs, through different platforms. According to the definition by the Saudi MOE, the basic elements of distance education

include the following: (a) an educational environment where the teacher and student(s) are separated by physical distance; (b) an electronically mediated delivery of instruction (i.e., satellite, video and/or audio broadcast, pictures, computer technology and/or multimedia); and (c) synchronous and asynchronous instruction (MOE, 2020a, 2020f).

The reliance on distance education in the field of learning disabilities in Saudi public schools is a promising topic, and it is difficult to completely judge the success or failure of this experience in the light of COVID-19. The researcher conducted this exploratory study, using a survey based on the relevant literature and on the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) model, to examine the reality of using distance education from the viewpoints of teachers of SLDs in a Saudi city during COVID-19. The SWOT model is an analysis tool used to monitor educational institutions and the experiences of individuals for development and strategic planning, and it stands for four elements—that is, strengths (S), weaknesses (W), opportunities (O), and threats (T)—related to a specific phenomenon measured by the opinions of specific groups (Chrusciel, 2011; Hughes & Wearing, 2017)—in this case, distance education—based on the opinions of teachers of SLDs.

Research Purpose and Rationale

The first stream of the research purpose was to reveal the level of SWOT of distance education based on the opinions of teachers of SLDs. The second stream of the research purpose was to assess the relationship between the teachers' views regarding distance education based on the SWOT model and their use of distance education types before and after COVID-19. It is worth mentioning that collected data were not used to make judgments, generalizations, evaluations or critiques of the local experience or government efforts in light of this crisis. Rather, the results of the current study may help to contribute to developing distance education for SLDs in the future by considering their teachers' voices. The researcher hopes in this study to inspire and help educators and leaders make informed decisions to address the corresponding challenges and to maximize the benefits of distance education for SLDs through the SWOT model.

Research Questions

Two main questions were used to address the highlighted goals and to guide the methodology of this research:

1. What is the level of reality of using distance education during COVID-19 from the point of view of teachers of SLDs and based on the SWOT model?
2. Is there a statistically significant relationship ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the reality of using distance education based on the SWOT model from the viewpoint of teachers of SLDs and their use of distance education types before and during COVID-19?

Overview of the Saudi Experience of Distance Education During COVID-19

Although the experience of Saudi Arabia with distance education for SLDs is relatively recent, it was not new to the educational system as a whole. Distance education had existed for a long time in some Saudi universities, where the education system by affiliation was a form of remote education (Shuaib & Mohammad, 2014). However, distance education for SLDs started officially in early 2020 after the emergence of COVID-19. The MOE has used a variety of methods to maintain remote learning during the pandemic through educational platforms available to all students, including SLDs, their teachers, and parents.

iEN National Education Portal

iEN is a free virtual learning community that supports digital learning and provides reliable electronic services for students, teachers, school leaders, supervisors, and parents. These services include study plans, electronic courses, recorded lessons, supportive materials, classroom activities, self-evaluation tools, guidance, and a question bank. iEN includes 23 satellite channels for all levels from K to 12 to support sign language. iEN lessons have also been provided on YouTube with an explanation of all levels of education, as well as on a broadcasting platform through the Arabsat satellite. MOE has also confirmed that iEN TV begins live broadcasting for secondary students at 7 a.m., whereas live broadcast for kindergarten and elementary students begin at 3 p.m. These programs are repeated around the clock. iEN helps teachers to use virtual classrooms to produce knowledge and to make it easier for parents to be supportive of their children's learning in their homes (MOE, 2020b).

My School Platform (Madrasati)

My School Platform (<https://schools.madrasati.sa/>) is a free electronic interactive platform directed to all students at all levels of education in general education. This platform includes virtual lessons reaching more than 86,208,941 lessons for public and private schools (MOE, 2020e). The MOE continued to rely on this platform until 2021. This platform provides multiple enrichment tools and provides mentors for student progress and electronic tests. Teachers can record attendance for virtual lessons, and students can submit assignments. Public, private and international schools all benefit from these services (MOE, 2020e). MOE

(2020e) also stated that the Madrasati platform provides more than 62,000 educational resources and interactive experiences that support synchronous and asynchronous learning. It also contains tools for scientific and cognitive measurement and evaluation. This platform provides question banks with more than 100,000 documented questions for teachers across various academic subjects. It also allows teachers to create questions measuring learning outcomes and performance (MOE, 2020c).

Education for Students With Learning Disabilities Before and During COVID-19

During COVID-19, the remote education of SLDs has been the responsibility of the MOE. Student attendance at schools has been rare or almost nonexistent due to precautionary measures in response to safety issues and parents' concerns.

The Saudi MOE defined learning disabilities based on Kirk's definition, which states that a learning disability is a disorder in one or more of the basic psychological processes that include the understanding and use of written or spoken language, which appears in disorders of listening, thinking, speaking, reading and writing (spelling, expression, and calligraphy), and mathematics that are not due to reasons related to intellectual, hearing, visual disabilities or other types of disabilities, learning circumstances or family upbringing. (Kirk, 1962, as cited by MOE, 2020a, p. 12)

Before COVID-19, SLDs in Saudi public schools received full face-to-face education with their peers in general classrooms for at least 80% of their school day, and they spent the rest of their school day receiving individual academic support or explication and direct instruction from their teachers in special education classrooms with small groups of students who have homogeneous academic characteristics and needs (MOE, 2020e, 2020d). These students receive the needed accommodations based on their individual educational plans. Consequently, many teachers of SLDs may encounter various experiences during COVID-19. Distance education in the field of learning disabilities is a part of the expected change in the future educational system and cannot be avoided in the achievement of development under Saudi Vision 2030, which calls for digital transformation in the educational sector and provides free and high-quality instruction for SLDs. If stakeholders and decision makers consider teachers' opinions and reflections on distance education during the pandemic, actions are more likely to be taken to address challenges and develop the infrastructure and available resources to effectively meet the needs of SLDs when using distance education after COVID-19.

Considerations of Distance Education in the Field of Learning Disabilities

Research findings have indicated that using distance education in the field of learning disabilities has advantages, disadvantages, and relevant considerations. For instance, in terms of accessibility and communication, remote instruction provides a chance to bridge the gap between home and school. Distance education has developed as a critical part of education as SLDs may be homebound due to medical reasons or future school closures (Hirsch & McDaniel, 2021). However, providing digital equity for SLDs, especially those in rural and urban areas to access technology including devices and the internet represents a challenge and concern for teachers (Tremmel et al., 2020). On the other hand, if SLDs are at home with their parents or caregivers, teachers can lead individualized education program (IEP) meetings to ensure that students can make progress to the maximum extent possible and to review accommodations and modifications, but the direct support and interaction might be missing in some cases due to the nature of the learning environment, such as asynchronous sessions, the low socioeconomic status of students, or the unique needs of these students (Hebert et al., 2020; Hirsch & McDaniel, 2021; Tremmel et al., 2020). Moreover, teachers of SLDs can continue to address IEP goals in an online format by holding one-on-one and small group sessions using various platforms and coordinator-shared resources and responsibilities with general education teachers and ongoing training through digital sources, such as Google Drive or Zoom. With these technologies, teachers can support students using platforms that are user friendly and available on mobile devices (Hirsch & McDaniel, 2021). However, these advantages and disadvantages may vary widely based on the students' needs and teachers' perspectives and experiences.

Views of Teachers of SLDs Regarding Distance Education in a SWOT Model

The SWOT acronym refers to strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats, and it was originally a model developed for business and industry, but it is equally useful for education, community health, development work, and even personal growth (David, 1993). The SWOT model can be described as an estimation technique used by individuals or institutions, and it has a long track record of effectiveness to determine whether a specific approach or experience is appropriate for a specific situation (Hughes & Wearing, 2017). One of the essential advantages of this model is its simplicity and applicability to different levels of work (David, 1993; Hughes & Wearing, 2017). SWOT helps deal with normal and unusual situations in schools and other institutions or systems by providing a tool to discover internal and external factors that affect the workforce and quality of provided services (Hughes & Wearing, 2017).

The SWOT model provides a simple way to communicate about an initiative, program, or practice, and an excellent way to organize the information collected through studies or surveys. In the current research, SWOT as an analytical method refers to identifying the strengths (advantages and benefits) and weaknesses (disadvantages and challenges) of distance education within general education schools for SLDs and identifying the opportunities and threats that exist outside of these schools and that affect the use of distance education for these students. As developing a full awareness of the situation of using distance education with SLDs helps in strategic planning and informed decisions based on teachers' real experiences during COVID-19, SWOT can provide helpful insights at any stage of educational effort regarding distance education based on the opinions of teachers of SLDs. This analysis can be used to do the following:

- Explore possibilities for new efforts or solutions to the problems related to using distance education for SLDs.
- Make decisions about the best school initiatives—trends and options that are made clear to teachers when they define the chances of success in the context of the threats to success.
- Identifying possible change locations—if schools are at a juncture or crossroads, they can take stock of strengths and weaknesses and can show priorities as well as possibilities.
- Modifying and refining plans in the middle of the track—a new opportunity may open a wider horizon for teachers, researchers, and decision-makers, whereas a new threat may lock schools from a way that existed before at school and district level.

Methodology

A quantitative exploratory research design was used to address the research purpose. Quantitative methods are often described as a way to maximize the opportunities of obtaining reliable, valid, and objective results (Creswell, 2014; Fraenkel et al., 2011). The data was collected by using a survey tool. A survey in quantitative research is one of the most common tools used to collect data from a representative sample of the population (Fowler, 2009). The current exploratory survey research could help pave the way for conducting further explanatory research focusing on measuring the impact and effectiveness of distance education for SLDs.

Participants

The study population consisted of 152 teachers of SLDs working in public elementary schools in Al-Ahsa Governorate in the Eastern Province of Saudi Arabia. The purposeful sampling was used to recruit the participants. This sampling technique allows us to explore a phenomenon from a specific group of individuals who could provide holistic information and an in-depth understanding of the targeted phenomenon, which in this study is the use of distance education during COVID-19 with SLDs (Creswell, 2014). Teachers who did not have experience using distance education were excluded from the study. The researcher sent a digital link of the survey tool, produced using the Google Forms feature, to the whole population via their work e-mails and professional groups on WhatsApp. The link included a question to the intended teachers regarding their desire to participate in the study. An approval form was also submitted to all possible participants via the same link. Although purposeful sampling was used, it is worth mentioning that the targeted teachers were available and willing to be part of the study in order to communicate their experiences and opinions about using distance education meaningfully. Therefore, the teachers who agreed to participate were given the right to opt out. A total of 41 teachers stated their desire to complete the survey, whereas 90 teachers stated that they did not wish to participate in the study.

Participating teachers had different characteristics. Some 59% were female teachers, whereas 41% were males. As for number of years of teaching experience, six teachers had less than 5 years, 26 teachers had between 5 to 9 years, seven teachers had between 10 to 14 years, and only two teachers had more than 14 years. A total of 28 teachers had bachelor's degrees in special education and specialized in learning disabilities, 12 had master's degrees in special education and specialized in learning disabilities, and only one teacher had an educational diploma in teaching SLDs.

Instrumentation: Scale of Reality of Using Distance Education in Light of COVID-19 Based on a SWOT Model

The researcher designed a survey scale to measure teachers' views on the use of distance education. The scale was developed based on the SWOT model and relevant literature on distance education for SLDs. The scale was reached in its initial form of 37 items under SWOT dimensions: (a) strength (S), which represents the advantages of distance education and consists of eleven items, (b) weaknesses (W), which represent the disadvantages of distance education and included nine items, (c) opportunities (O), which refer to future trends positively affecting distance education for SLDs, and included nine items, and, finally, (d) threats (T), which represent the challenges or negative aspects influencing the use of distance education for SLDs, and included eight items. A 5-point Likert scale was used to measure each dimension (1 = *strongly disagree*, 2 = *disagree*, 3

= *both agree and disagree*, 4 = *agree*, and 5 = *strongly agree*). The survey started off with open-ended demographic questions focusing on the level of education, teaching experience, and usage of distance education before and during COVID-19. The entire survey, including the demographic section, required approximately 10 to 15 min to complete.

Research Variables

The research included the following variables.

Dependent variables:

- (1) strengths (S): advantages of using distance education
- (2) weakness (W): the disadvantages of using distance education
- (3) opportunities (O): future trends that affect the advantages and disadvantages of using distance education
- (4) threats (T): challenges or negatively affecting aspects of the advantages and disadvantages of using distance education

These variables are categorical, ordinal qualitative variables, where the arithmetic mean of the dimension was classified in proportion to Likert's grading of its paragraphs as between 1.00 and 1.49, strongly disagree; between 1.50 and 2.49, disagree; between 2.50 and 3.49, neutral; between 3.50 and 4.49, agree; and between 4.50–5.00, strongly agree.

Independent variables:

- (1) The type of distance learning used before COVID-19, with seven levels:
 - Did not use it, coded 0
 - specific-platform, coded 1
 - virtual classes, coded 2
 - applications, coded 3
 - multimedia, coded 4
 - some of the above, coded 5
 - all of the above, coded 6
- (2) The type of distance learning during COVID-19, also with seven levels:
 - platform private, coded 1
 - virtual classes, coded 2
 - applications, coded 3
 - multimedia, coded 4
 - some of the above; coded 5
 - all of the above, coded 6

These are categorical, ordinal qualitative variables.

Validity and Reliability of the Scale

Content Validity

To establish content validity, the researcher sent the scale to a group of three experts who hold doctoral degrees and are experienced and specialized in the fields of special education, distance education, and general education. The researcher also sent the scale to two teachers of SLDs. The experts were asked to review and evaluate the scale in terms of clarity of meaning, linguistic construct, and relevance of each item under each dimension. All comments by the experts that they agreed upon (67%) were taken into consideration in light of the results of verifying the content validity of the scale, which centered on reformulating some items, and adding an item to the W dimension. Thus, the total number of items in the revised scale was 38.

Internal Consistency Validity

The researcher applied the scale to the pilot sample consisting of 15 teachers from outside the target sample (7 males and 8 females) to calculate* the corrected item-total correlation coefficients[†] for the relationship of the items with their dimensions. The corrected correlation coefficient values for the relationship of items for the four dimensions (S, W, O, and T) ranged between 0.48–0.68, 0.52–0.75, 0.50–0.59, and 0.48–0.74,

*Statistically, the item-corrected correlation coefficient is more accurate than the Pearson correlation coefficient; where it takes into account the specificity of the item in that it has a categorical gradation arranged in contrast to being continuous, and because it is calculated after deleting the value of the response to the relevant item from its dimension in the scale; which gives a clear connection to the relationship of the item with its dimension from the point of view of teachers.

[†] $R_i = (COV(X_i, P) - S_i^2) / (S_i \tilde{S}_i)$

respectively. The values related to the validity of the construction (consistency of homogeneity between the contents of the items belonging to the dimensions of the scale separately) and the calculated values of the item discrimination coefficients (corrected correlation of items' relationship with the dimensions of the use of distance education during the pandemic) did not fall below the critical value of 0.47761, which is calculated according to the t-test[‡] that examines the null hypothesis "They do not differ." The value of the corrected correlation coefficient was calculated from zero ($\alpha = 0.05$) at 13 degrees of freedom in light of the size of the pilot sample; which indicates the quality of building items of the dimensions of the scale among the targeted sample.

Reliability

To calculate the internal consistency of the scale dimensions, the Cronbach's alpha (α)[§] equation was used based on the data of the first application on the pilot sample. The values of the internal correlation coefficients for the dimensions below the main diameter of their matrixes were 0.83 for the S dimension with a mean of 0.313, 0.85 for W with a mean of 0.364, 0.75 for the O dimension with a mean of 0.248, and 0.77 for the T dimension with an arithmetic mean of 0.29. These values show variation in the strength of the internal consistency stability coefficients according to Cronbach's α for the scale dimensions, which indicates a standard of the homogeneity of the items' contents within the relevant dimensions and the nonviolation of the homogeneity of the variance among the pilot sample on the contents of the items under each dimension. To calculate the stability index of the scale dimensions, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated according to the test-retest method, and the scale was reapplied to the pilot sample 2 weeks after the first application. The values for the S, W, O, and T were 0.85, 0.83, 0.78, and 0.81, respectively. The values of the Pearson correlation coefficients for the relationship between the first and second applications did not fall below the critical value of 0.47761, computed according to the t-test at 13 degrees of freedom. Therefore, these values show the stability index as one of the convergent reliability indicators that measures the same characteristic at the various levels of possession of the scale's pilot sample.

Correction Key of the Scale

The revised instrument included 38 items. The raw scores for the scale dimensions are S = 11–55, W = 10–50, O = 9–45, and T = 8–40. To evaluate the level of the scale dimensions and their items, researchers do not depend on collocation means due to their inaccuracy as a statistical indicator in the decision-making process (i.e., if one of the two statistical models with absolute or relative increment is adopted) and because they adopt discretionary criteria that have no tangible numerical weight, according to clear-cut statistical indicators (Duran, 1980). Thus, the two absolute or relative gradations create a susceptibility to questioning the reliability of the decisions during the development of cutoff scores (classification) of the means for the participants' viewpoint, vis-à-vis the measured dimensions and relevant items, because they give vague and nonconclusive judgments. Therefore, the descriptive nature may confuse the presentation and discussion of the research question results, whereas the current study is classified as a detailed study. The specificity of each item is concerned with the dimensions of a scale, which requires reliance on statistical indicators that take this specificity into account. The researcher adopted the statistical model with standard grading, based on statistical significance for the value of a t-test for a single sample^{**}, in the process of evaluating the level of SWOT dimensions from viewpoint of the participants—that is, by comparing their means with the theoretical arithmetic mean (threshold) whose value is 3 for each dimension. If the value of the t-test (a) is greater than the cutoff score with a statistically significant difference ($\alpha = 0.05$), and the participants' responses on the dimension and its items are characterized as having a high level; (b) greater or less than the cutoff score with a statistically significant difference at $\alpha = 0.05$, and the participants' responses on it and its items are characterized as having a medium level; and (c) smaller than the cutoff score with a statistically significant difference at $\alpha = 0.05$, and the participants' viewpoint of the items is low.

Data Collection Procedures

[‡] $t = (r \times \sqrt{df}) / \sqrt{1 - r^2}$; where: $df = n - 2$; n : size of pilot study.

[§] $\rho_{standardized} = (k\bar{r}) / [1 + (k - 1)\bar{r}]$; where k is the number of items, \bar{r} is the mean of correlation Coefficients among items of dimension.

^{**}The preference of a single-sample t-test in making decisions; this test takes into account a set of statistical indicators; the arithmetic means (calculated and theoretical) and the standard error of the arithmetic mean computed in light of deviation and sample size according to its equation one sample t-test = $((\bar{x} - \mu) / ((sd / \sqrt{n})))$ compared to the two statistical models with absolute progressiveness and the relative based on the arithmetic mean only.

The process of data collection started with obtaining approval from the Institutional Review Board and permission from the Special Education Department in Al Ahsa District. Then, the researcher sent a digital link to the targeted participants via work emails. In the same survey link, the consent form was provided to the participants, and they were informed about the purpose of the study. To increase the rate of response among the potential participants, the researcher sent the link twice a few weeks apart.

To ensure participants' confidentiality, data were collected and kept safe on a password-protected computer. Data and approval forms will be destroyed 3 years after the completion of the study, and only the researcher can access the data. Participants did not receive compensation or obtain additional benefits from participating in this study.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis of the data was carried out by using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences as follows:

1. To answer the first research question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the dimensions and items of the scale were calculated from the participants' viewpoint, followed by a t-test for one sample compared to the theoretical arithmetic mean, and the size of the Cohen effect (practical significance) was calculated for each dimension from a distance Hedges' correction was used to correct the size of the effect, taking into account the order of the items within its dimension according to the descending t-test values.

2. To answer the second research question, the observed frequencies were calculated within the Likert scale categories for the four dimensions and items of the scale, including their items within the teachers' responses regarding using distance education before and during COVID-19, the standard remainder^{††}, and (χ^2) test values for independence^{‡‡}, and the modified standard remainder^{§§}.

Results and Discussion

RQ1. What is the level of reality of using distance education during COVID-19 from the point of view of teachers of SLDs based on the SWOT model?

Strengths of Using Distance Education

Table 1 shows that the level of advantages of using distance education in light of the COVID-19 pandemic from the teachers' point of view was high because its arithmetic mean was greater than the theoretical arithmetic mean by a statistically significant difference ($\alpha = 0.05$) and with a high effect size. Based on the responses on the scale, the teachers either *strongly agreed* or *agreed* that using distance education had many advantages. This result is consistent with the idea of using technology as a mode to provide a wide range of pros that represent a solution to the interruption of in-person education for SLDs at its multiple stages due to the pandemic (Ayad, 2020). The researcher classified the detailed data related to S items on the survey into two levels based on the statistical significance of the t-test as follows:

1. High level: Items 8, 11, 9, and 3 had a high effect size, and item numbers 6, 1, and 10 had a medium effect size; also, item 7 had a small effect size due to the fact that the arithmetic mean was greater than the theoretical arithmetic mean by a statistically significant difference ($\alpha = 0.05$). Teachers of SLDs believe that distance education benefits them and their students in terms of facilitating communication, complements traditional education, enhances self-learning skills, and contributes to the attainment of spatial stability among expatriate teachers, which reflects the quality of their instruction. These advantages confirmed the research findings that accessibility and flexibility are prominent features of digital learning environments for both learners and teachers, and these are guaranteed by meeting the unique needs of learners that could not be met in some face-to-face educational settings (Bienkowski et al., 2012; Center on Online Learning and Students With Disabilities [COLSD], 2012, Rose & Meyer, 2002).

2. Medium level: Items 5, 4, and 2 had a trivial or dummy effect size because their arithmetic mean was greater or smaller than the theoretical mean by a difference that was not statistically significant ($\alpha = 0.05$). Based on the teachers' responses, it seemed that distance education is not necessary in helping SLDs achieve individual goals, facilitating communication between SLD and general education teachers, and addressing the shortage of SLD teachers. This perspective can be understood as follows: Although the teachers agreed that

^{††}Standardized Residual = $(o - e)/\sqrt{e}$; Significant if its value is greater than or less than (± 1.96).

^{‡‡}Test of Independence $\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(\sum_{j=1}^3 \left((o_{ij} - e_{ij})^2 / e_{ij} \right) \right)$

^{§§}Adjusted standardized Residual_{ij} =

$(o_{ij} - e_{ij}) / \sqrt{e_{ij} \times (1 - (r_i/n)) \times (1 - (c_j/n))}$; Significant if its value is greater than or less than (± 1.96).

distance education had some advantages, they also agreed there could be potential barriers related to schools, teachers, families, students, or the limited power of distance education to benefit from those advantages (COLSD, 2012). Some barriers are embodied in this paper under the sections of results related to the W and T dimensions of distance education.

Table 1

Results of One-Sample t-test of the Means for the Strengths of Using Distance Education From the Viewpoints of the Teachers in Light of COVID-19 Compared to the Theoretical Arithmetic Mean (3), and Hedges' Correction for the Size of the Cohen Effect

Rank	ID	Strengths*	Mean	SD	One-sample t-test		Hedges' correction for Cohen's d effect size	
					Comp. Value	Level	Value	Strength
<i>Distance education is characterized by the ease of communication with the teacher and the student even outside official working hours, where there are many means of instant communication</i>								
1	8		3.88	0.90	6.248*	High	0.9573	High
<i>Distance education for the category of learning disabilities is complementary in its characteristics to traditional education</i>								
2	11		3.66	0.69	6.083*	High	0.9321	High
<i>Distance education helps to provide students with self-learning skills that sometimes cannot be acquired through traditional education</i>								
3	9		3.71	0.84	5.367*	High	0.8223	High
<i>Distance education achieves spatial stability for expatriate teachers of SLDs, which is reflected in the quality of teaching</i>								
4	3		3.83	1.00	5.323*	High	0.8156	High
<i>Distance education teaches digital skills to SLDs</i>								
5	6		3.71	0.90	5.025*	High	0.7700	Moderate
<i>Distance education prepares SLD teacher programs to keep pace with the trend toward digital transformation in education</i>								
6	1		3.68	0.96	4.554*	High	0.6978	Moderate
<i>Distance education has the flexibility of presenting the educational material throughout the day or all days of the week, as it helps students to manage their study time</i>								
7	10		3.61	0.95	4.130*	High	0.6327	Moderate
<i>Distance education is diverse in proportion to the diversity of learning disabilities</i>								
8	7		3.41	1.02	2.592*	High	0.3972	Small
<i>Distance education helps to achieve individual educational goals in innovative ways compared to traditional education methods</i>								
9	5		3.15	0.94	1.000	Moderate	0.1532	Trivial
<i>Distance education enhances communication between general education and SLD teacher programs</i>								
10	4		3.02	1.11	0.141	Moderate	0.0216	Trivial
<i>Distance education fills the shortage in the number of teachers of SLDs</i>								
11	2		2.95	1.07	-0.292	Moderate	-0.0447	Trivial
<i>Whole for First Dimension</i>								
			3.51	0.57	5.694**	High	0.8725	High

* $p \leq 0.05$

Weakness of Using Distance Education

The researcher noted from Table 2 that the level of negative aspects of using distance education during the pandemic for SLDs based on the teachers' responses was high. This increase can be explained because the mean was greater than the theoretical arithmetic mean by a statistically significant difference ($\alpha = 0.05$) and with a high effect size. Interestingly, all items of the W dimension were classified within a high level, where the items 19, 18, 21, 22, 13, 20, 16, and 17 had a high effect, item 14 had a medium effect, and item 15 had a small effect. In other words, the teachers mostly reported that the virtual environment does not meet the unique needs of SLDs as first disadvantage and lacks direct interactions as second disadvantages. This perspective could be true in some cases—for example, due to the intensity of disabilities of students who need to have more accessible features that promote more interactions, and the need of professional development training for teachers to meet the needs of these students in a virtual environment. The participant teachers also thought that distance education may increase the possibility that students will hide their disabilities as one of the disadvantages. The researcher believe that students might hide their disabilities because they have not been

trained to advocate for themselves to receive technical support or as a coping strategy in a virtual environment. Designing objective assessments, lack of school infrastructure, stress due to device use, time consumed while preparing materials, and mentoring progress represent additional challenges that teachers face in distance education. These challenges are consistent with what had been reported regarding the challenges and obstacles of online learning and distance education for students with disabilities at the international level (Ferri et al., 2020; Lassoued, 2020; UNESCO, 2021). Additionally, it is logical for these challenges to be obvious, especially for Saudi teachers of SLDs who participated in this survey, due to the modernity of distance education experience during the pandemic in particular.

Table 2

Results of One-Sample t-test of the Means for the Weakness of Using Distance Education From the Viewpoints of the Teachers in Light of COVID-19 Compared to the Theoretical Arithmetic Mean (3), and Hedges' Correction for the Size of the Cohen Effect

Rank	ID	Weakness	Mean	SD	One-Sample t test		Hedges' correction for Cohen's d effect size	
					Comp. Value	Level	Value	Strength
<i>Virtual distance learning environments may not meet the unique social needs of the learning disability group (such as direct sensory communication with the teacher and peers) compared to traditional learning environments</i>								
1	19		4.34	0.73	11.793*	High	1.8070	High
<i>One of the disadvantages of distance education is the lack of a real study environment that raises the direct academic response to the SLDs compared to traditional educational environments</i>								
2	18		4.07	0.65	10.609*	High	1.6256	High
<i>Distance education may increase the chances of students hiding the reality of academic disability</i>								
3	21		4.22	0.76	10.292*	High	1.5770	High
<i>In distance education, it may be difficult to make an objective assessment of the category of learning disabilities</i>								
4	22		4.20	0.78	9.790*	High	1.5001	High
<i>Lack of the school infrastructure (such as the lack of computers or poor Internet connection speed) is one of the weaknesses related to the use of distance education with the category of learning disabilities</i>								
5	13		4.17	0.77	9.717*	High	1.4889	High
<i>Distance education may lead to stress for the student due to the time student spends on smart phones and other electronic devices to follow the required study materials and tasks</i>								
6	20		4.15	0.82	8.914*	High	1.3658	High
<i>Distance education may require more time than traditional education in preparing content</i>								
7	16		3.83	0.80	6.611*	High	1.0130	High
<i>Distance education may require more time than traditional education in monitoring the performance of students in learning disabilities programs</i>								
8	17		3.73	0.81	5.806*	High	0.8896	High
<i>The lack of knowledge of the teacher's background about the use of distance education with SLDs category of additional weaknesses</i>								
9	14		3.68	0.88	4.977*	High	0.7626	Moderate
<i>One of the disadvantages of distance education is the high financial cost compared to traditional or blended education</i>								
10	15		3.41	0.95	2.800*	High	0.4291	Small
<i>Whole for second dimension</i>			3.98	0.51	12.205*	High	1.8701	High

* $p \leq 0.05$

Opportunities of Using Distance Education

The findings indicate that the level of future trends toward the use of distance education was high in the light of the pandemic based on the teachers' responses. Statistically, this finding can be explained by the mean of O, which was greater than the theoretical arithmetic mean by a statistically significant difference ($\alpha = 0.05$) and with a high effect size. The items belonging to the O dimension were classified within two levels, as shown in Table 3:

1. High: Most items (31, 30, 29, 26, 28, 32, 27, and 24) had a high effect size due to the theoretical arithmetic mean by a statistically significant difference ($\alpha = 0.05$). Teachers believe that distance education maximizes the opportunities of conducting research, develops smart applications, addresses attitudes toward digital transforming, remedies the shortcomings of professional preparation programs,

develops assessment tools, and provides supportive laws. Practically, teachers' responses regarding O seemed to be consistent with the Saudi sustainable goals for quality of research and equality of educational opportunities for SLDs, considering the digital transformation trends and data investment in the educational sector (Saudi Vision 2030, 2019).

2. Medium: Item 25, which was ranked in the ninth place in terms of the future opportunities of distance education, with a small trace size because of the mean, was higher than the theoretical arithmetic means by a statistically nonsignificant difference ($\alpha = 0.05$). These data showed that the distance education experience for SLDs based on the teachers' responses help to somehow to understand the reality of school challenges and problems, but it was ranked in the last place of the opportunities list based on the teachers' responses.

Table 3

Results of One-Sample t-test of the Means for the Opportunities of Using Distance Education From the Viewpoints of the Teachers in Light of COVID-19 Compared to the Theoretical Arithmetic Mean (3), and Hedges' Correction for the Size of the Cohen Effect

Rank	ID	Opportunities	Mean	SD	One-sample t-test		Hedges' correction for Cohen's d effect size	
					Comp. Value	Level	Value	Strength
<i>The use of distance education for SLDs during the pandemic opens research horizons for those interested</i>								
1	31		4.15	0.53	13.920*	High	2.1329	High
<i>One of the benefits of distance education during the pandemic is the expansion of the development of smart applications suitable for SLDs</i>								
2	30		4.17	0.59	12.760*	High	1.9552	High
<i>The experience of distance education during the pandemic contributes to improving teachers' negative attitudes toward using technology with SLDs</i>								
3	29		4.10	0.58	12.048*	High	1.8461	High
<i>The experience of distance education during the pandemic is an opportunity to enact laws and legislation that guarantee the right to adapt educational resources to the SLDs</i>								
4	26		3.90	0.66	8.709*	High	1.3344	High
<i>The experience of distance education during the pandemic is an opportunity to remedy the shortcomings of the professional preparation programs</i>								
5	28		3.85	0.69	7.906*	High	1.2113	High
<i>One of the lessons learned from using distance education during the pandemic has been the development of more objective assessment methods for SLDs</i>								
6	32		3.93	0.75	7.864*	High	1.2049	High
<i>Distance education during the pandemic period helps develop the school staff and its physical systems related to learning disabilities programs</i>								
7	27		3.71	0.64	7.054*	High	1.0809	High
<i>Distance education with SLDs during the pandemic prepares society to accept the trend toward digital transformation for the post-pandemic period</i>								
8	24		3.71	0.78	5.788*	High	0.8869	High
<i>The distance education experience for SLDs helps to understand the reality of schools in terms of identifying related problems and challenges</i>								
9	25		3.24	0.83	1.881	Moderate	0.2883	Small
<i>Whole for third dimension</i>			3.86	0.39	14.284*	High	2.1886	High

* $p \leq 0.05$

Threats of Distance Education

Although the data reflected that the teachers perceive distance education as a promising trend delivery mode of instruction for their SLDs, their response on the survey also reflected their concerns about this trend. Table 4 notes that the level of the negatively affecting aspects were high of the challenges of using distance education for SLDs. Additionally, all relevant items of the dimension were classified within a high level of the aspects that represent the T because their arithmetic mean was greater than the theoretical arithmetic mean by a statistically significant difference ($\alpha = 0.05$). It not surprising that the teachers expressed their concerns of the internal and external threats of distance education, such as teachers' and families' negative attitudes toward digital transformations, the impact of socioeconomic student backgrounds, low self-motivation of SLDs, and low direct social interactions (see Table 4 for more specific examples) because distance education still represents a new experience at the local educational level.

Table 4

Results of One-Sample t-test of the Means for the Threats of Using Distance Education from the Teachers' Viewpoints In Light of COVID-19, Compared to the Theoretical Arithmetic Mean (3), and Hedges' Correction for the Size of the Cohen Effect

Rank	ID	Threats	Mean	SD	One-sample t-test		Hedges' correction for Cohen's d effect size	
					Comp. Value	Level	Value	Strength
The negative attitudes of the teacher toward using distance education can affect the quality of meeting the needs of learning disabilities programs								
1	35		4.17	0.50	15.141*	High	2.3200	High
The low self-motivation of the student with learning disabilities hinders the effectiveness of using distance education								
2	39		4.27	0.81	10.063*	High	1.5420	High
Difficult environmental factors (such as living in remote areas without access to Internet services or limited family income) may deprive a segment of SLDs from distance education opportunities compared to their peers								
3	38		4.32	0.88	9.599*	High	1.4707	High
The absence of a clear mechanism for activating distance education for learning disabilities programs in the school may hinder their implementation								
4	34		4.24	0.83	9.595*	High	1.4702	High
Exaggeration in the trend toward distance education may limit the nature of direct social interaction between SLDs and their peers in traditional educational environments								
5	40		4.02	0.79	8.301*	High	1.2719	High
The lack of experience of teachers of SLDs in using distance teaching methods weakens their ability to manage this type of education efficiently								
6	36		4.02	0.85	7.707*	High	1.1809	High
The failure of parents with learning disabilities to accept the idea of distance education hinders achieving their children's individual educational goals								
7	37		3.98	0.99	6.329*	High	0.9697	High
Orientation toward distance education may lead companies to reduce the use of free applications directed to the SLDs and their families								
8	41		3.68	0.76	5.782*	High	0.8860	High
Whole for Fourth Dimension								
			4.09	0.49	14.111*	High	2.1621	High

* $p \leq 0.05$

RQ2. Is there a statistically significant relationship ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the reality of using distance education based on the SWOT model from the SLD teachers' viewpoints and the type of distance education used before and during COVID-19?

The (χ^2) test values for the independence of the relationship between the observed frequencies within the Likert scale categories (*strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, strongly agree*) were calculated for each of the dependent variables (S, W, O, and T) related to the reality of using distance education in light of COVID-19 from the teachers' perspective and the levels of the type of distance education used before the pandemic ("I did not use it," "special platform," "virtual classes," "applications," "multimedia," "all of the above," or "some of the above"; see Table 5).

Table 5

The Results of the Test (χ^2) of the Independence of the Observed Frequencies Within the Likert Scale Categories of the SWOT Dimesons and the Levels of the Type of Distance Education Used Before COVID-19

Relation between Type of Usage of Distance Education Before COVID-19 and SWOT	χ^2	df	Sig.
Strengths(S): Advantages of using distance education	27.68	18	0.07
Weakness (W):Disadvantages of using distance education	14.65	12	0.26
Opportunities (O): Future trends enhancing advantages and limiting disadvantages of using distance education	17.07	12	0.15

Threats (T): Aspects that negatively decrease and increase the disadvantages

37.15* 12 0.00

* $p \leq 0.05$

Table 5 shows there is no statistically significant relationship ($\alpha = 0.05$) between each of the dimensions S,W, and O as related to the reality of using distance education in light of COVID-19 from the participants' point of view and the type distance education used before the pandemic. However, it is clear from Table 5 there is a statistically significant relationship ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the dimension of the negatively affecting aspects of the pros and cons of using distance education (T) from the participant's viewpoints and the type of distance education used before the pandemic; which indicates to the independence of the observed frequencies within the Likert grading categories (*strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, strongly agree*) for T based on the participants' responses in terms of the levels of the different uses of distance education before and after the pandemic ("I didn't use it," "private platform," "virtual classes," "apps," "multimedia," "all of the above," or "some of the above). To determine the direction of the relationship, the adjusted standard remainder was calculated for the observed frequencies within the Likert scale of dimension categories according to the levels of the type of distance education used before the pandemic. The standard remainder was calculated to determine the significance of the frequencies observed for the Likert scale categories of the dimension and their percentages within the levels of the type of distance education used before the pandemic (see Table 6).

Table 6

The Results of the Adjusted Standard Residual and the Standard Residual of the Observed Frequencies Within the Likert Scale Categories of the Threats of Using Distance Education In Light of the COVID-19 Pandemic, Based On the Participants' Responses According To the Type of Distance Education Used Before the Pandemic

Type of Usage of Distance Education Before Covid19	Statistic	Threats			Total	
		N.S.	A.	S.A.		
I did not use distance education	Count		17	6	23	
	% Within Row		73.9%	26.1%	100%	
	Std. Residual	-7.7*	9.3 ⁽²⁾	-1.7	0	
	Adj. Std. Residual	-2.0*	1.2	-0.1		
Private platform	Count		2		2	
	% Within Row	100%			100%	
	Std. Residual	1.3	-0.7	-0.7	0	
	Adj. Std. Residual	5.2*	-2.0*	-0.9		
Virtual Classes	Count		1	1	2	
	% Within Row		50%	50%	100%	
	Std. Residual	-0.7	0.3	0.3	0	
	Adj. Std. Residual	-0.4	-0.5	0.8		
Apps	Count		1	1	2	
	% Within Row	50%	50%		100%	
	Std. Residual	0.3	0.3	-0.7	0	
	Adj. Std. Residual	2.4*	-0.5	-0.9		
Multimedia	Count			1	1	
	% Within Row			100%	100%	
	Std. Residual	-0.3	-0.3	0.7	0	
	Adj. Std. Residual	-0.3	-1.4	1.7		
All the above methods	Count		2	1	3	
	% Within Row		66.7%	33.3%	100%	
	Std. Residual	-1.0	1.0	0.0	0	
	Adj. Std. Residual	-0.5	0.0	0.3		
Some of the above methods	Count		6	2	8	
	% Within Row		75%	25%	100%	
	Std. Residual	-2.7*	3.3 ⁽³⁾	-0.7	0	
	Adj. Std. Residual	-0.9	0.6	-0.1		
Total	Count		3	27	11	41
	% Within Row		7.3%	65.9%	26.8%	100%
	Std. Residual	-10.7*	13.3 ⁽¹⁾	-2.7*	0	

* $p \leq 0.05$

It is clear from Table 6 that the adjusted standard residual's values that exceed the value of +1.96 refer to the cells responsible for the relationship between them. In the case of moving from teachers whose type of distance education used before the pandemic was "applications" to their counterparts, for whom their type of distance education used before the COVID-19 pandemic was a "special platform," their views on the negative aspects of the pros and cons of using distance education become more neutral on the Likert scale. Note that the Likert category of the grading dimension among the teachers was the highest possible according to the values of the standard remainder that exceeded the value of +1.96 as follows: (a) within a category that agrees with a percentage of 65.9%, regardless of the type of education used remotely before the COVID-19 pandemic, (b) within the category of agreement with a percentage of 73.9) among the teachers whose type of distance education used before the pandemic was "I did not use it," and (c) within the category of strongly agree with a percentage of 75% among the teachers whose type of use of distance education before the pandemic was "some of the above." This result can be explained according to the novelty of the distance education experience of teachers of SLDs in public schools, in which they tend to show more concerns regardless of the type of distance education used.

The (χ^2) test values for the independence of the relationship between the observed frequencies within the Likert scale categories (*strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, strongly agree*) were calculated for each of the dependent variables (S, W, O, and T) related to the reality of using distance education in light of the COVID-19 pandemic from the teachers' point of view and the levels of the type of distance education used before the pandemic ("I did not use it," "special platform," "virtual classes," "applications," "multimedia," "all of the above," or "some of the above") are shown in Table 7.

Table 7

The Results of the Test (χ^2) of the Independence of the Observed Frequencies Within the Likert Scale Categories of the SWOT Dimensions and the Levels of the Type of Distance Education Used While COVID-19

Relation Between Type of Usage of Distance Education While COVID-19 and SWOT	χ^2	df	Sig.
Strengths (S): Advantages of using distance education	15.16	12	0.23
Weakness(W): Disadvantages of using distance education	10.45	8	0.24
Opportunities (O): Future trends enhancing advantages and limiting disadvantages of using distance education	43.07*	8	0.00
Threats (T): Aspects that negatively decrease and increase disadvantages	9.31	8	0.32

* $p \leq 0.05$

Table 7 shows there is no statistically significant relationship ($\alpha = 0.05$) between each of the dimensions (S,W, and T) related to the reality of using distance education in light of the COVID-19 pandemic from the teachers' point of view and the type of distance education used during the pandemic. While it is clear from Table 7 that there is a statistically significant relationship ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the O dimension, future trends toward the pros and cons of using distance education, from the teachers' point of view and the type of distance education that they used during the pandemic. To determine the direction of the relationship, the adjusted standard remainder was calculated for the observed frequencies within the Likert scale categories of dimension according to the levels of the type of distance education used during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The standard remainder was calculated to determine the significance of the frequencies observed for the Likert scale categories of the O dimension and their percentages within the levels of the type of distance education used during the pandemic, each on sharpness. Table 8 shows the values of the adjusted standard residual that exceeded the value +1.96 refers to the cells responsible for the relationship between them. In the case of transmission from study individuals whose answers were "all of the above" in regard to the type of distance education they used during the pandemic, compared to their counterparts who answered the same, their views regarding O moved from the *agree* category to the *strongly agree* category of the Likert scale. Note that the categories of Likert grading of the dimension among the teachers are the highest possible according to the values of the standard remainder that exceeded the value of +1.96 are as follows: (a) within the category of agree with a percentage of 80.5% regardless of the type of their use for distance education during the pandemic, (b) within the *agreeable* category with a percentage of 86.7% among the study individuals who answered *some of the above* about the type of distance education they used during the COVID-19 pandemic, (c) within the category of *strongly agree* with a percentage of 75% among the study members whose answer was *with a special platform* about the type of distance education they used during the COVID-19 pandemic, and (d) within the category of *strongly agree* with a percentage of 100% among the study members whose answer was *in virtual classes* about the type of distance education they used during the COVID-19 pandemic.

This result indicates that the use of distance education during the pandemic, regardless of the type used, opened enabled the teachers to see opportunities associated with distance education, unlike before the pandemic when they perceived distance education as a threat. This observation would encourage seeing the positive side of the pandemic that has allowed teachers to explore and experience different types of education while recognizing the positives and future directions of distance education in the field of learning difficulties

Table 8

The Results of the Adjusted Standard Residual and the Standard Residual of the Observed Frequencies Within the Likert Scale Categories of the Dimension of Opportunities According to the Type of Distance Education Used During COVID-19

Type of Usage of Distance Education During COVID-19	Statistic	Opportunities			Total
		N.S.	A.	S.A.	
Private platform	Count	4	12		16
	% Within Row	25%	75%		100%
	Std. Residual	-1.3	6.7 ^{*(3)}	-5.3*	0
	Adj. Std. Residual	1.1	-0.7	-0.8	
Virtual classes	Count		5		5
	% Within Row		100%		100%
	Std. Residual	-1.7	3.3 ^{*(4)}	-1.7	0
	Adj. Std. Residual	-1.1	1.2	-0.4	
Apps	Count	1	3		4
	% Within Row	25%	75%		100%
	Std. Residual	-0.3	1.7	-1.3	0
	Adj. Std. Residual	0.4	-0.3	-0.3	
All the above methods	Count			1	1
	% Within Row			100%	100%
	Std. Residual	-0.3	-0.3	0.7	0
	Adj. Std. Residual	-0.5	-2.1*	6.4*	
Some of the above methods	Count	2	13		15
	% Within Row	13.3%	86.7%		100%
	Std. Residual	-3.0*	8.0 ^{*(2)}	-5.0*	0
	Adj. Std. Residual	-0.5	0.8	-0.8	
Total	Count	7	33	1	41
	% Within Row	17.1%	80.5%	2.4%	100%
	Std. Residual	-6.7*	19.3 ^{*(1)}	-12.7*	0

* $p \leq 0.05$

Limitations

Although Saudi Arabia followed uniform precautionary measures and used similar alternatives for distance education with SLDs in the public schools, and although this study has promising results, these results cannot be generalized across the Saudi teachers of SLDs due to the nature of the study, the setting, and the participants. The first main limitation of this study is that it was limited exclusively on Al-Ahsa governance. The other limitation was in the distribution of the survey via the link to the targeted sample, which gave the ability to opt-out of the study. This decreased the desired number of the participants. Therefore, these limitations can be addressed when replicating this study in future.

Conclusion

The preventive measures Saudi Arabia took to limit the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic had a role in shifting from traditional education to distance education for all students, including those with learning disabilities, in public schools. This study aimed to explore the views of teachers of SLDs about strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in regard to using distance education in the light of the pandemic. The results revealed that the most prominent strengths related to distance education for both SLDs and their teachers from the teachers' viewpoints included ease of communication, integration with traditional education, enhancing self-learning skills, and contributing to achieving spatial stability for expatriate teachers. The majority of teachers believed that the virtual environments did not meet the unique needs of SLDs because these environments lacked direct social interactions compared to the traditional classrooms. On the other hand, the teachers believed that distance education during COVID-19 enhanced opportunities of conducting research, designing smart applications, addressing negative attitudes toward digital transformation, developing

preparation programs and assessment tools, and supporting laws to ensure the quality of distance education of SLDs. In contrast, the teachers believed there was a range of internal and external threats affecting the distance education for SLDs. Furthermore, there was a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of the threats, negatively affecting the aspects of the pros and cons, of using distance education, and the type of distance education the teachers used before the pandemic, as well as a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of education opportunities related to distance education and the type of distance education used during the pandemic ($\alpha = 0.05$).

This study recommends conducting further research on the perspectives of SLDs, their teachers, and parents in different cities and countries after the pandemic by using the SWOT model of analysis. Such research would contribute to understanding the reality of using distance education and promoting the exploration of solutions to maximize the advantages and overcome the issues of distance education in the learning disabilities field, which is expected to be the part of the future phase of education at the local and international level after COVID-19.

Notes

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